

Strategies for Navigating Post-Election Raw Material Price Surges in Indonesia

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Abstract

This study dives into the complex factors underlying the rise in raw material costs following Indonesian elections. We hope to shed light on the complexity of this occurrence by investigating the intricate interplay of political, economic, and market factors. We illuminate the causes driving post-election raw material price changes using a qualitative research that combines insights from relevant economic theories and empirical evidence. Our findings emphasize the important impact of political dynamics, demand-supply mismatches, policy adjustments, market speculation, and infrastructure development on raw material prices. Understanding these dynamics allows governments and market actors to devise targeted policies to reduce the negative consequences while capitalizing on the opportunities afforded by post-election price increases.

Keywords: *Post-election dynamics; Raw material prices; Economic fluctuations; Policy implications*

Introduction

Following elections in Indonesia 2024, a country on the verge of revolution, a strange phenomena emerges: a dramatic increase in raw material costs. But why does this surge happen, and what subtle dynamics lurk beneath the surface? Why has Indonesia, a country with enormous potential and various landscapes, become the site for such economic turmoil? These questions entice us to go deeper, to uncover the secrets that surround Indonesia's economic situation after the election.

As we engage on this voyage of study, we are met with several fundamental concerns that require careful consideration. When we look at the aftermath of elections, we see how complicated the interplay between politics, economics, and the forces that shape commodity prices is. Uncertainty about election results causes waves of caution across the economy, resulting in supply chain disruptions and pricing volatility. This pattern emphasizes the need to understand why election-related uncertainty has such a significant impact on the market. Furthermore, the boost in demand, fuelled by increased government spending and consumer optimism following the election, strains supply chains and causes shortages, ultimately driving raw material prices skyrocketing. These

considerations highlight the interaction between political transitions and economic conditions, underlining the importance of investigating how policy changes, such as changes in trade tariffs and investment laws, affect raw material markets and send shockwaves through global trade flows.

Furthermore, elections provide fertile ground for market speculation, resulting in speculative activity that exacerbates price swings. It is fascinating to consider how market speculation grows during this period, as the market reflects all available information via the prism of the Efficient Market Hypothesis. Understanding these processes is critical to developing a better understanding of the complex interplay between politics, economics, and the forces that influence commodity pricing. Examining the influence of recent elections on food commodity prices, we see considerable rises in a variety of categories. On February 16, 2024, premium rice, medium rice, red onions, garlic, curly red chili peppers, bird's eye chili peppers, pure beef, commercial chicken meat, chicken eggs, consumption sugar, packaged cooking oil, and wheat flour all increased in price (Joharsoyo & Sedayu, 2024).

According to the National Food Agency (Bapanas), premium rice has increased by 1.26%, reaching Rp 16,100 per kilogram. Similarly, medium rice prices have risen by 0.14%, reaching Rp 13,970 per kilogram. Notably, the highest price for premium rice was reported in Papua Pegunungan Province, at Rp 23,420 per kilogram. Curly red chili peppers are currently priced at Rp 59,120 per kilogram, up 5.55% from the previous week, while bird's eye chili peppers have increased by 6.18% to Rp 54,460 per kilogram. Furthermore, red onions have risen by 1.73%, now costing Rp 33,490 per kilogram, while garlic has grown by 1.33%, reaching Rp 38,760. In the meat category, pure beef has risen by 0.03% to Rp 134,060 per kilogram, while commercial chicken meat has increased by 1.71% to Rp 36,900. Chicken eggs have also climbed by 1.54%, to Rp 29,100. These price swings are the result of market dynamics and supply-demand imbalances caused by post-election circumstances (Joharsoyo & Sedayu, 2024).

Examining the delicate relationship between elections, market dynamics, and commodity prices provides significant insights into the intricacies of political and economic interactions. And, amidst all of these whys, one question stands out: Why is Indonesia, with its rich tapestry of natural riches and strong economy, at the center of this post-election turmoil? We must seek answers here, amid Indonesia's dynamic political scene and rising economic possibilities. Only by comprehending the intricate interplay of political, economic, and social forces at work in Indonesia will we be able to unravel the complexity of the post-election spike in raw material prices and map a road toward stability and prosperity.

Method

This qualitative study attempts to delve into the complex web of causes influencing Indonesia's post-election spike in raw material prices. This study aims to provide a thorough understanding of the phenomenon's drivers by combining ideas from an exhaustive literature review, engaging in expert debates, and evaluating reliable internet news sources. We use a qualitative lens to examine the intricate interplay of political, economic, and market factors in order to illuminate the mechanisms that drive raw material prices after elections. The goal of this research is to provide

policymakers, corporations, and stakeholders with essential information to help them negotiate the hurdles and capitalize on the opportunities afforded by these oscillations.

Result and Discussion

The rise in raw material costs following Indonesian elections is a complex issue that requires further investigation. The following discussion will dive into the various factors driving this trend, drawing on pertinent economic theory and empirical evidence.

Political Dynamics

Political dynamics in the post-election period have far-reaching consequences for economic decision-making processes, as described in scholarly literature. Downs' Economic Theory of Democracy (1957) provides useful insights into how firms deal with the uncertainty surrounding election results. According to Downs, firms adapt their approaches based on their expectations for election results, expecting probable policy shifts under new regimes. The prospect of legislative changes creates an environment of uncertainty, encouraging firms to exercise caution as they negotiate the changing political landscape.

Dixit and Londregan (1996) go into greater detail about the relationship between political uncertainty and economic decision-making, highlighting how anxiety about election results can cause supply chain disruptions and pricing volatility. Their findings emphasize the necessity of understanding how political dynamics influence market participants' behavior, particularly in terms of investment and supply chain management.

Furthermore, wider economic theories, such as Keynesian Economics, give light on how government policies influence economic outcomes. Keynes (1937) emphasizes the role of government intervention in stabilizing economies, particularly during times of uncertainty. From this perspective, the uncertainty around election results might increase the need for government action to maintain economic stability, influencing businesses' strategic decisions even more.

Furthermore, behavioral economic insights provide a more comprehensive picture of how individuals and organizations deal with uncertainty. Kahneman and Tversky's (1992) prospect theory proposes that in uncertain situations, people are risk-averse, preferring to avoid future losses rather than seek profits. This behavioral tendency toward risk aversion might influence company decision-making processes in the post-election period, contributing to cautious conduct and slowness in making large investments.

Political dynamics in the post-election period have far-reaching implications for economic decision-making processes, influenced by theories such as Downs' Economic Theory of Democracy, Dixit and Londregan's political uncertainty research, Keynesian Economics, and behavioral economics insights. Understanding the relationship between political uncertainty and economic behavior allows firms and policymakers to better manage the intricacies of post-election scenarios and avoid the risks associated with uncertain political landscapes.

Demand-Supply Dynamics

A wide range of factors influence demand-supply dynamics in the post-election period, with implications for market equilibrium and raw material pricing. Blanchard and Perotti (2002) emphasize the importance of elections in increasing economic activity, particularly through increased government spending and consumer optimism. This rush in demand, driven by anticipation of improving economic conditions under new governments, can put a strain on supply chains, resulting in raw material shortages and price increases.

Furthermore, Rostow's Stages of Economic Growth (1959) give a framework for understanding economies' developmental trajectory, particularly during post-election times. According to Rostow, growing countries go through several stages of growth, each marked by changes in economic structure and consumer habits. Post-election periods are frequently associated with periods of fast industrialization and infrastructure development, as newly elected governments concentrate investment in critical industries to spur economic growth and provide job opportunities.

The increase in demand for raw materials following elections is worsened by businesses' pre-election hoarding, which is driven by uncertainty about future policy choices. Businesses may decide to increase their stocks of raw materials and finished goods as a protection against potential interruptions or policy changes following elections. This boost in demand ahead of the election, combined with increased spending post-election, further strains supply chains and exacerbates shortages, resulting to rising raw material costs.

Furthermore, supply chain management theory provides useful insights into the dynamics of demand and supply in the post-election period. Lee *et al.* (1997) described the Bullwhip Effect, which shows that tiny changes in demand can be exacerbated as they move upstream via supply chains. During the post-election period, increasing demand from government spending efforts and consumer confidence can accentuate supply chain disruptions, resulting in exaggerated changes in raw material prices.

Moreover, demand-supply dynamics in the post-election period are influenced by increased government expenditure, consumer optimism, pre-election hoarding, and the developmental trajectory of economies, as described in Rostow's Stages of Economic Growth. Understanding these dynamics, together with insights from supply chain management theory, is critical for forecasting and reducing the effects of post-election changes in raw material costs.

Policy Dynamics

Policy dynamics are essential in defining the post-election scenario, with far-reaching consequences for raw material markets. Following elections, governments frequently implement important policy alterations, such as changes in trade tariffs, investment laws, and taxation policies, which can have far-reaching implications for market dynamics. Baldwin (2018) emphasizes the influence of policy changes on raw material markets, notably the implementation of protectionist measures or changes to taxation laws. Protectionist policies, such as taxes or quotas on imported commodities, can disrupt global trade patterns, altering raw material availability and pricing. Similarly,

changes in taxation policies, such as import levies or export subsidies, can have an impact on domestic industry competitiveness and alter supply-demand dynamics in raw material markets.

Knight's Uncertainty Theory (1921) explains how policy uncertainty increases market volatility, contributing to price swings in raw material markets. During the post-election period, market participants may exhibit cautious behavior due to uncertainty about the implementation of new policies or the continuation of existing ones. Businesses may postpone investment choices or modify production strategy until the regulatory climate becomes clearer. This caution can lead to supply chain interruptions and price volatility as market participants manage the uncertainties of regulatory changes.

Furthermore, regulatory economics provides vital insights into the link between policy dynamics and market results. Regulatory capture theory, for example, holds that special interest groups can influence regulatory rules, resulting in outcomes that benefit specific industries or stakeholders. In raw material markets, regulatory capture can emerge as rules that favor domestic producers over foreign competitors, influencing raw material supply and pricing.

Moreover, post-election policy dynamics can have a considerable impact on raw material markets through changes in trade tariffs, investment laws, and tax policies. The implementation of protectionist measures or changes in taxation policy can disrupt global trade flows and affect the price of imported raw commodities. Furthermore, policy uncertainty exacerbates market volatility, causing swings in raw material prices as market participants adapt to shifting regulatory frameworks. Understanding these processes, together with insights from regulatory economics, is critical for forecasting and responding to the consequences of policy changes on raw material markets.

Market Dynamics

Market dynamics during the post-election period are characterized by increased speculation and changeable investor moods, which can have a substantial impact on commodity prices. Elections serve as a spur for market speculation, as investors anticipate prospective policy changes and their impact on raw material markets. Keynesian Economics, as defined by Keynes (1937), emphasizes the role of market sentiment and speculative activity in determining price changes. According to Keynesian theory, investor perceptions and expectations have an important role in shaping market prices, especially during times of uncertainty such as elections. Speculative activities fueled by expectations of governmental shifts or economic changes can cause sharp variations in raw material prices as investors react to anticipated possibilities and hazards.

In contrast, Fama (1970) proposed the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH), which provides an alternative perspective on market dynamics. The EMH holds that market prices represent all available information, making it difficult for investors to continuously outperform the market through speculation. According to this hypothesis, market participants' activities reflect election-related changes and other pertinent information, resulting in sensible pricing and little opportunities for arbitrage.

However, it is critical to note that both Keynesian Economics and the Efficient Market Hypothesis provide useful insights into market behavior following the election. While Keynesian Economics emphasizes the role of investor feelings and speculative activities in short-term price movements, the Efficient Market Hypothesis emphasizes markets' efficiency in processing information and reflecting it in long-term asset values.

Furthermore, behavioral finance theories like prospect theory and herd behavior can help explain market dynamics in the post-election period. Prospect theory implies that investors may behave in a risk-seeking or risk-averse manner depending on how choice outcomes are framed, whereas herd behavior proposes that investors may follow the behaviors of others without considering fundamental issues.

Moreover, post-election market dynamics are influenced by a combination of investor attitude, speculative activity, and market players' efficient information processing. While Keynesian Economics emphasizes the role of sentiment and speculation in driving short-term price movements, the Efficient Market Hypothesis highlights markets' ability to represent all available information in asset values over time. Understanding these dynamics is critical for evaluating raw material price variations and making sound investment decisions in the wake of elections.

Infrastructure Dynamics

Infrastructure dynamics during the post-election era are defined by an increase in construction project investment, which is driven by government commitments and public demand for better infrastructure. This behavior can be better understood by applying Samuelson's Accelerator Theory of Investment, which he introduced in 1939. The Accelerator Theory of Investment holds that changes in aggregate demand, particularly increases in investment spending, cause corresponding changes in demand for capital goods such as construction materials. In terms of post-election infrastructure development, greater public expenditure in projects such as road construction, bridge construction, and urban growth drives up demand for raw materials such as steel, cement, and asphalt.

According to Samuelson's theory, when demand for capital goods rises, companies increase production of those products. However, due to the limited capacity of existing supply chains and manufacturing facilities, addressing this additional demand may be difficult. The imbalance between expanding demand and constrained supply capacities might put upward pressure on raw material prices. In addition, the increase in infrastructure development projects following the election exacerbates supply-demand imbalances in the raw materials market. As construction activities increase and demand for resources such as steel and cement outpaces supply, shortages may emerge, sending prices even higher.

Furthermore, the impact of government policies and regulations on infrastructure dynamics cannot be underestimated. Post-election governments frequently prioritize infrastructure construction in order to keep campaign pledges, encourage economic growth, and meet public expectations for better public services. Policies aimed at speeding infrastructure projects, such as

faster approval processes or enhanced public-private partnerships, might exacerbate the demand for building materials. Likewise, the impact of infrastructure dynamics on raw material pricing extends beyond the domestic market, as increasing demand for building materials has the potential to influence global commodities markets. For example, an increase in steel production to suit a certain country's infrastructure needs may result in higher demand for iron ore, influencing global supply and pricing dynamics.

Moreover, infrastructure dynamics during the post-election period are influenced by increased public investment in construction projects, which raises demand for raw materials like as steel and cement. The Accelerator Theory of Investment explains how growing demand encourages production while straining existing supply capacities, ultimately influencing raw material pricing. Understanding these dynamics is critical for governments, investors, and industry stakeholders as they negotiate the potential and challenges posed by post-election infrastructure development efforts.

Subsequently, the post-election spike in raw material costs in Indonesia is a multifaceted phenomenon influenced by political, demand-supply, policy, market, and infrastructure factors. Policymakers and market participants must have a detailed grasp of these dynamics, informed by applicable economic theories and empirical evidence, to negotiate the challenges and possibilities posed by such swings.

Navigating Indonesia's Post-Election Raw Material Price Dynamics

To effectively tackle the post-election spike in raw material costs in Indonesia, a detailed study that delves deeper into the underlying causes and potential remedies is required. This multidimensional subject necessitates a complete understanding guided by economic theory, empirical evidence, and practical insights.

1. Political Dynamics

Elections are watershed occasions in any country's political landscape, frequently accompanied by a wave of uncertainty that spreads throughout numerous sectors, including the economy. According to Downs' Economic Theory of Democracy (1957), firms adjust their strategy in expectation of election results. For example, industries that rely largely on government contracts may reduce investments or take a wait-and-see attitude until the new administration's priorities are clear. This cautious behavior by market participants can lead to supply chain interruptions and price volatility.

Furthermore, the aftermath of elections causes significant policy shifts that resonate across the economy. Changes in trade tariffs, investment laws, and fiscal policies have a significant impact on raw material markets. For example, if a newly elected government sets tariffs on imported items, it may encourage domestic production of specific raw materials, causing shifts in supply and demand dynamics. Policy uncertainty, as noted by Knight's Uncertainty Theory (1921), can exacerbate market volatility, causing prices to vary as investors and businesses adjust to the new regulatory regime.

Consider the hypothetical situation of a presidential election in Country X. In the run-up to the election, car companies may postpone investments in traditional combustion engine technology in favor of electric vehicles (EVs), anticipating probable changes in environmental legislation. This shift in policy may disrupt the supply chain for raw minerals like lithium, cobalt, and nickel, which are critical components of EV batteries. As a result, prices for certain raw commodities may rise or fall unexpectedly, reflecting market uncertainty about the election outcome and following policy changes.

2. Demand-Supply Dynamics

Following elections, there is frequently a rise in economic activity, fueled by higher government spending and greater consumer confidence. This increase in demand might have a knock-on effect on other areas of the economy, including the raw resources market. For example, government-led infrastructure projects and stimulus programs targeted at increasing employment and investment can cause a considerable increase in demand for building materials such as steel, cement, and asphalt. Similarly, consumer spending may rise as individuals gain confidence in the country's future orientation under the new leadership, resulting in increased demand for goods and services across industries.

Businesses' pre-election stockpiling complicates demand-supply dynamics. Businesses may choose to increase their stocks of raw materials and finished goods in anticipation of probable interruptions or legislative changes following the election. This boost in demand before the election, along with increased expenditure afterward, has the potential to strain supply networks and cause market shortages.

Additionally, in developing economies such as Indonesia, the period immediately after elections is frequently accompanied by a period of fast industrialization and infrastructural development. According to Rostow's Stages of Economic Growth (1959), countries going through economic transition experience an increase in demand for raw resources to drive infrastructural projects and industrial expansion. New roads, bridges, airports, and other infrastructure projects, for example, necessitate large amounts of steel, concrete, and other raw materials for construction. This increased demand puts further strain on the raw material supply, resulting in price increases and supply chain disruptions.

Consider the situation of Country Y's freshly elected government, which announces ambitious intentions to improve its transportation system. In response to this statement, construction companies scale up their activities, causing a boom in demand for steel and concrete. However, the unexpected spike in demand outpaces domestic providers' capacity, resulting in market shortages. As a result, construction projects are delayed, and steel and cement prices have skyrocketed. This scenario highlights the complex interplay of political events, economic policies, and supply-demand dynamics in setting raw material prices after elections.

3. Market Dynamics

A multitude of factors influence market dynamics after elections, including investor sentiment, speculative activity, and market players' efficient information processing. One important feature of market dynamics is the role of speculative activity in causing price volatility. Elections frequently generate an environment of uncertainty, with investors hoping to profit from anticipated policy changes and their possible impact on raw material markets. For example, investors may speculate on the outcome of an election and change their investment strategy accordingly, causing raw material prices to fluctuate. This phenomena is consistent with Keynesian Economics' discoveries (Keynes, 1937), which highlight the role of market attitudes and speculative activity in influencing price changes.

However, the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH), developed by Fama in 1970, provides a different perspective on market dynamics. According to the EMH, markets efficiently absorb all available information into asset prices, resulting in reasonable pricing with little possibilities for investors to consistently exceed the market. From this perspective, election-related developments, such as policy announcements and political outcomes, are quickly reflected in raw material pricing, ensuring that they appropriately reflect current market conditions.

Consider the following scenario: an election in Country X results in a change of administration, with a declared commitment to renewable energy programs. Investors, anticipating a change toward green energy policies, began to put more money into renewable energy businesses and commodities like solar panels and lithium for batteries. This speculative behavior raises the short-term pricing of key basic resources, reflecting market expectations of future policy changes. However, when more information becomes available and the new government's policies take effect, market prices adapt to reflect the true impact on supply and demand dynamics. This example demonstrates how speculative actions can impact short-term price changes, while efficient information processing by market participants eventually leads to sensible pricing over the long term.

4. Infrastructure Dynamics

Infrastructure dynamics after elections have a significant impact on raw material markets, as governments begin on ambitious infrastructure projects to fulfill campaign promises and meet popular expectations. One important facet of infrastructure dynamics is the increase in infrastructure development efforts that normally happens following elections. Newly elected governments frequently prioritize infrastructure projects to boost economic growth, create jobs, and improve public services. For example, a government may declare plans to develop new highways, bridges, airports, and railways to upgrade transportation infrastructure and improve regional connectivity.

The Accelerator Theory of expenditure, introduced by Samuelson in 1939, sheds light on how higher public expenditure boosts demand for construction materials such as steel, cement, and asphalt. According to this hypothesis, a rise in aggregate demand caused by government spending on infrastructure projects results in a corresponding increase in investment to meet the

increased demand. As a result, construction businesses increase their raw material production, putting pressure on existing supply capacities and driving up raw material prices.

Assume Country Y has national elections, and the newly elected government announces a substantial infrastructure development plan to modernize the country's transportation network. The plan includes building new roadways, expanding current airports, and developing high-speed train connections between important cities. As building on these projects begins, there is an increase in demand for raw materials such as steel for bridge construction, cement for road paving, and aggregate for concrete manufacturing. This rise in demand exceeds existing supply capacity, resulting in shortages and price hikes in the raw material markets. The ensuing rise in raw material prices raises the overall cost of infrastructure projects and influences investment decisions in linked businesses.

Furthermore, tackling the post-election spike in raw material costs in Indonesia necessitates a better understanding of the complex mechanisms at work. By examining these elements through the perspective of applicable economic theories and empirical facts, policymakers and market participants can devise tailored strategies to limit the negative consequences and capitalize on the opportunities afforded by such volatility.

Conclusion

The post-election spike in raw material prices in Indonesia reveals a web of complications, highlighting the delicate interplay of political, economic, and market variables. We have uncovered the multiple elements that contribute to this phenomena, giving insight on its underlying mechanics and implications. Political factors appear as a crucial driver, with elections triggering a period of increased uncertainty that ripples across the economy. As firms adjust their strategy in anticipation of the election results, supply chain interruptions and price volatility occur. Policy changes, such as changes in trade tariffs and investment rules, exacerbate the problem by sending shockwaves through global trade flows and increasing market volatility.

Elections boost economic activity by increasing government spending and consumer optimism. The rise in demand, along with pre-election stockpiling, stresses supply networks and causes shortages, eventually driving raw material prices higher. Furthermore, increased industrialization and infrastructure development after the election increase demand for raw resources, increasing supply-demand imbalances. Market dynamics provide a new degree of complexity, with elections offering fertile ground for speculative activities that exacerbate price swings. While market sentiment and speculative activity cause short-term swings, the Efficient Market Hypothesis ensures that prices appropriately reflect all available information in the long run.

Governments prioritize infrastructure projects to boost economic growth, which further shapes raw material markets. The growth in demand for construction materials strains existing supply capacity, resulting in shortages and price increases. Furthermore, tackling the post-election spike in raw material costs in Indonesia necessitates a thorough grasp of the complex mechanisms at play. Policymakers and market participants can develop targeted methods to reduce the negative

consequences of such oscillations while capitalizing on the opportunities they bring by leveraging insights from economic theories and empirical data. Thus, navigating Indonesia's post-election raw material pricing dynamics necessitates a comprehensive approach guided by a thorough understanding of the many factors that influence this phenomenon.

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